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STUDY OF THE CHANGE OF THE HETEROGENEITY CHARACTERISTICS OF THE COLLECTORS ON THE BASIS OF GEOPHYSICAL DATA

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Abstract

The heterogeneity of the horizon depends on the oil saturation, porosity coefficient, average layer thickness, effective thickness, etc. learn more using data. To determine the coefficient of separation characterizing the inhomogeneity of the layers. Determining the degree of heterogeneity of the horizon that constitutes the research object according to the values of this coefficient. Determination of inhomogeneity through these methods allows to assess the prospect of exploitation of the horizon. This, will help quantify hydrocarbon production.

In addition, a map of lithological differences in different layers was constructed to study the heterogeneity of the horizon.

Oil saturation effective thickness maps were compared with lithological, differentiation maps. Such a comparison allows for the correct placement of impact wells. Determining different types of collectors on the territory makes it possible to more accurately calculate the oil yield coefficient of the layers [1].

Keywords: porosity, heterogeneity, effective thickness, oil saturation, permeability, average layer thickness, sandy, variation, collector.

Before studying the geological heterogeneity of layers in oil fields, correlation should be made using geophysical complexes that allow to distinguish the same layers in all well sections. In the horizons, the sandy layers are the same according to their mineralogical composition. If it is not possible to separate the horizons in them, then the material composition of the

clay layers should be studied in detail so that this separation allows comparison of the sandy layers.

In order to study the geological heterogeneity of the horizon in detail, lithological differentiation maps are drawn up for individual layers. These maps usually show the distribution areas of sandy bodies, siltstones and clays (argillites), (figure 1, a, b, c, e, d).

Figure 1. Lithological differentiation maps of horizon layers (a, b, c, d):
1 – sandstones; 2 – siltstones; 3 – clays

In addition, oil-saturated effective thickness maps of the formations are constructed. These thicknesses at the inner limits of the oil contour on this layer will not differ in any way from the total effective thickness. In the zone between the inner and outer oil contours, the accuracy of the determination of the effective oil saturated thickness will directly depend on the accuracy of the determination of the water-oil contact surface [2].

Usually, the oil-saturated effective thickness map is combined with the lithological differentiation map for the purpose of oil reserve calculation and field development planning. This greatly simplifies the determination of the volume of different types of collectors. Such reconciled maps allow for accurate placement of impactor wells. Increases the effective effect on oil layers.

Due to lithological differences and isopachyte maps, it is possible to accurately determine the volume of rocks within the oil contour of formations (sandstones, siltstones and other types of rocks) compared to conventional methods. At the same time, zones without collectors are defined as a result of siltation of sandy-siltstone layers or their replacement by impermeable rocks.

The information obtained about the volume of different types of collectors allows more reliable calculation of the oil yield coefficient of the formations.

When studying non-homogeneous strata, usually the stratified structure is modeled in the vertical direction and the variation of physical properties of the rocks across the stratum is not taken into account. Therefore, in laboratory conditions, it is necessary to model layers in such a way that they have both a layered structure

and horizontal inhomogeneity. At the same time, in order to improve the modeling principles of non-homogeneous porous media, it is necessary to observe the laws of compression of oil in close to natural conditions.

During the observations, it was found that the sandstones are not characterized by a lens-like and layered structure. They were found to have different permeability in neighboring areas, ranging from a few cm to tens of cm in size. Such a feature indicates that the rock is heterogeneous [3].

The clay layers separating the sandy layers differ in their continuity, and when they are wedged in different areas of the bed, the so-called "joint zone" areas are separated on the maps. The latter are important for the development of the field. So, these zones are not only the paths of vertical migration of hydrocarbons, but at the same time they are currently carrying out the hydrodynamic connection of one layer with another.

According to the "Joint Zones" maps, it is possible to determine the amount of clay units located in the structure of the area where they are wedged.

Thus, the heterogeneity of productive horizons is studied through geological-geophysical methods. It is used in the design and analysis of oil fields.

As it is known, the collectors are not stable according to their thickness on the field, and they are also not stable according to their volume and filtration characteristics in addition, in individual cases, there is also a chance of delamination of layers and layers. As a result of this change in the inhomogeneity of the layers, the assimilation of the resource in fertile horizons proceeds at different speeds. This, in turn, leads to the watering of reservoir layers for various reasons, the premature decommissioning of wells, and the loss of a certain amount of oil as a result [4].

In this regard, it is necessary to take into account the geological heterogeneity of the deposit during the design and control period of the development.

In our opinion, it is more appropriate to apply the statistical method in the quantitative study of the characteristics of the inhomogeneity of the collectors. This method can provide more correct and accurate information about the change of the geological heterogeneity characteristics of the reservoirs [6].

Let's give a brief description of the methodology to be used. To determine non-homogeneity, it is necessary to use a lot of information:

- C_{sand} - sandness;
- H_{e,t} - effective thickness;
- H_{a,l,t} - average layer thickness;
- K_{p,c} - porosity coefficient;
- K_{o,s,c} - oil saturation coefficient etc.

There are a lot of methods for the determination these parameters. With the average value of these quantities to study the geological problem

$$\bar{X}_n = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n X_i}{n_k}$$

- n_k) . The number of layers belonging to class k; i - number of layer; Σ - summary,

$$\sigma_{xk} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \bar{X}_k)^2}{n_k - 1}}$$

variation values,

$$K_{day} = X_{max} - X_{min}$$

variation coefficient (

$$W = \frac{\sigma_x}{\bar{X}} 100 \%$$

) . For this reason, such reporting

works were carried out for the Lower Girmaki Formation in the Surakhani field and the results are given in (Table 1). As can be seen from the table, such a report for LGF₁ (Lower Girmaki Formation 1), LGF₂ (Lower Girmaki Formation 2) and LGF₄ (Lower Girmaki Formation 4), horizons was performed on separate blocks.

Table 1

The values of the quantities obtained along the horizons of the Lower Girmaki Formation (LGF)

Parameters	Block, horizon						
	Mean, arithmetic mean and coefficient of variation	North+	South+	North+	South+	Nourth	South+
		center	east	center	east		
		LGF ₁	LGF ₁	LGF ₂	LGF ₂	LGF ₄	LGF ₄
H _{ef} ^{ave} (m)	M _{ave}	10	18.0	25.3	13.7	19.7	14.6
	σ	5.8	6.9	12.3	5.6	5.8	7.6
	W	57.7	38.0	48.0	40.0	29.0	51.0
h _{ef} ^{lay} (m)	M _{ave}	3.0	4.5	4.9	3.4	5.3	4.5
	σ	2.4	3.3	3.9	2.4	3.9	3.4
	W	80	74	79	71	74	76
C _{sand} (%)	M _{ave}	0.75	0.70	0.69	0.70	0.67	0.70
	σ	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.04
	W	5.0	5.0	5.0	4.0	5.0	5.0
K _p (%)	M _{ave}	21.8	21.0	19.7	20.4	21.0	19.3
	σ	3.6	4.1	4.0	3.3	4.1	4.3
	W	16.0	19.0	20.0	16.0	19.0	21.0
K _{o,s} (%)	M _{ave}	72.3	71.3	70.6	70.1	71.3	72.1
	σ	2.6	2.8	2.1	2.0	2.3	1.9
	W	3.0	3.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	2.0

It was found out from the researches that the inhomogeneity of the geological object is inversely proportional to the product of the change values (variation) of the porosity and oil-gas saturation coefficients of the rocks that make up the layer and layers.

The inhomogeneity coefficient characterizing the inhomogeneity for the determination of the inhomogeneity of the geological object, as well as the formula for determining the separation coefficient, were developed by us.

This methodology was applied to the LGF₁, LGF₂, LGF₄ horizons of the Surakhani field. We can express this feature with the formula below [5]:

$$K_{h.g} = W_p W_{o.s} / H_{ef}^{hor} h_{ef}^{lay} \quad (1)$$

$W_{v.p.c}$ - variation of pore coefficient;

$W_{v.o.s}$ - variation of oil saturation coefficient;

H_{ef}^{hor} – average effective thickness of the horizon;

h_{ef}^{lay} - average effective thickness of the layer;

It should be noted that the values of porosity and oil saturation coefficients vary widely over the horizon, so their variations are used in the report.

The main quantity characterizing the inhomogeneity can be taken as the separation coefficient (more precisely, the layer division coefficient) (R). Separation coefficient means the ratio of the total number of sand layers along the section of the wells included in the report to the product of the total average effective thickness of the total number of wells. We can write this in the form of a formula as follows [5]:

$$R = \frac{100 \sum m}{n H_{hor}^{ort}} \quad (2)$$

m - the sum of the number of sandy layers in the horizon (concentrated sum of the wells);

n - total number of wells;

$H_{a.t.h}$ - the total average thickness of the horizon.

The separation coefficient characterizes the inhomogeneity of the layers, and its large numerical value indicates the inhomogeneity of the operating object. This allows us to know in advance that there will be difficulties in the exploitation of such horizons.

Conclusions.

The largest separation and inhomogeneity coefficients were obtained in LGF₁ in the ("northern + central") block of the field. (although C_{sand} in this area coefficient is higher than others (0.75). This is reflected in (Table 2).

Table 2

Calculations for all horizons

Horizon	M	N	$H_{horizon}$. (average, m)	R, (1/m)	$K_{h.g}$
QAD ₁ (nouth+centre)	100	24	32.0	13.0	1.60
QAD ₁ (south+east)	95	27	33.0	10.7	0.70
QAD ₂ (nouth+centre)	92	38	51.0	4.7	0.32
QAD ₂ (south+east)	166	38	41.0	10.6	0.69
QAD ₄ (nouth)	59	16	37.0	10.0	0.55
QAD ₄ (south+east)	102	34	29.0	10.3	0.54

2. This allows us to note that in the future, when this horizon is put into operation, it will be more difficult to produce hydrocarbons from it than others.

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